

Research methodology

Leaf carbohydrate analysis—a simple method for integrating daily canopy photosynthesis

E. A. Conocono, T. L. Setter, and J. A. Egdane, IRRI

Current methods for assessing carbon assimilation require many photosynthesis measurements taken at different times during the day to get an accurate estimate on a daily basis. This is impractical and expensive in terms of labor and equipment, and it is sometimes impossible to do with more than one sample because of intermittent sunny and cloudy periods during the day.

Carbon assimilation during the day will be integrated by the amount of carbohydrate assimilated by tissues. The nonstructural carbohydrate (soluble sugars and starch) that the plant produces during the day can be quantified by taking the difference between plant carbohydrate content at 6 a.m., when little or no photosynthesis has yet occurred, and at 6 p.m., when the plant has undergone photosynthesis for that day. This method may give a better estimate of carbon assimilated during the day compared with photosynthesis measurements taken at one point in time.

We evaluated the relationship between plant carbohydrate content, daily canopy photosynthesis, and irradiance at the panicle initiation stage. The experiment used irrigated, direct seeded IR72. Light was varied using shade nets. Total soluble sugars was analyzed using anthrone reagent and starch by enzymatic hydrolysis with amyloglucosidase followed by glucose oxidase-peroxidase enzymes. Canopy photosynthesis was measured using a Licor 6200 portable photosynthesis system and a canopy frame (80 cm × 80 cm and 130-cm-high) with a removable top and four 120-mm-diameter battery-operated fans to facilitate equilibration and rapid mixing of gas. Each measurement took 15 s and each replicate was measured 3–6 times every 2 h from 6 a.m. to 6 p.m. at four different radiation levels.

1. Total nonstructural carbohydrate profile of stems and leaves during the day. Plants were unshaded and samples taken at 0-2 days after panicle initiation. (error bars = standard deviation)

There is a linear increase in leaf carbohydrates with time (Fig. 1). This trend is not present in stem carbohydrates, meaning that daily canopy assimilation is more related to leaf carbohydrate content than stem carbohydrate content. The stem acts as storage tissue and may contribute up to 40% or more of grain carbohydrates such that diurnal changes in stem carbohydrates will be relative to high background concentrations. In contrast, leaf carbohydrates are at lower concentrations, and sugars are presumably readily mobilized from these tissues. Hence, leaf carbohydrates better reflect the results of current photosynthesis.

A highly significant direct relationship exists between canopy photosynthesis per day and radiation ($r^2 = 1.00^{**}$), as well as between leaf carbohydrates and radiation ($r^2 = 0.99^{**}$) (Fig. 2). When leaf carbohydrate content and daily canopy photosynthesis are compared, we also find a highly significant correlation ($r^2 = 0.99^{**}$). Similar correlations were obtained in two other experiments.

Based on these results, we suggest that leaf carbohydrate analysis is suitable for

2. Correlation between daily canopy photosynthesis, net leaf carbohydrate content, and daily radiation. (error bars = standard deviation)

quantifying daily canopy photosynthesis, especially when conditions do not allow efficient and accurate photosynthesis measurements. ■

A weather-based empirical model to predict rice leaf blast in Thailand

S. B. Calvero, Jr., IRRI; A. Surin, RPRG-Department of Agriculture (DOA), Thailand; O. Pilansinchai, DOA, Thailand; and P. S. Teng, IRRI

Empirical models are important tools in rice disease management, especially in the context of sustainable agriculture. These models can guide farmers in choosing a disease management strategy to prevent an epidemic. For leaf blast, caused by *Pyricularia grisea*, models have been developed in some temperate countries where the disease naturally occurs. However, few of the models have been applied in actual production systems. In tropical countries such as Thailand, development of empirical models for rice blast is still in its early stages.

We used the multiple linear regression technique to generate an equation to serve as an empirical model to predict rice leaf blast on cultivar RD23. This model can be used as part of a blast management program in Thailand. The equation is based on leaf blast severity as the dependent variable assessed 32 d after sowing (DAS) from weekly sowings of the cultivar in 1993-94 under dry (upland) conditions at Uthong Field Crop Experiment Station, Suphanburi. Plants were grown and maintained in 1-m² plots. Ammonium phosphate fertilizer (16-20-0) was applied to the plots along with 100 kg N ha⁻¹.

For each category of leaf blast severity assessed, the likelihood of that severity correlating with a weather variable (e.g., rainfall frequency, number of days with relative humidity \geq 80%, mean maximum temperature) was estimated using WINDOW PANE, a weather variable searching computer program available at IRRI. This software served as an intercessory tool in developing the empirical model to better identify weather variables with direct effects on blast. The searching mechanism of WINDOW PANE is based on a series of time durations during which a particular weather variable occurs. For each time duration, correlation with leaf blast severity was estimated. Weather variables occurring at certain time durations that WINDOW PANE found to have high correlation with leaf blast severities were then chosen as independent variables in regression analysis.

A best fitting equation was based on the following selection criteria: high adjusted coefficient of determination (r^2), coefficient of variation (CV) < 25%, low predicted error sum of squares (PRESS), predictors with variance inflation factors (VIF) < 10, and regression coefficients (β 's) with significance level (P) \leq 0.05.

The best fitting equation used as an empirical model to predict percent leaf blast severity (Y) on RD23 is

$$Y = [56.184 - 8.261 \sqrt{\text{MMAX}} - 0.710(\text{MWS}^3)]^2$$

where MMAX is the mean maximum temperature ($^{\circ}$ C) at time durations from 40 d before sowing (DBS) to 14 DAS, and MWS is the mean windspeed from 40 DBS to 24 DAS. The equation has r^2 , CV, and PRESS values of 0.87, 11.62, and 23.86, respectively. All independent variables

Comparison of observed and predicted leaf blast severities observed 32 d after sowing on RD23. Uthong Field Crop Experiment Station, Suphanburi, Thailand.^a

Statistical parameter	Fitting sample (n = 20)	Validation sample (n = 6)
r	0.914**	0.955**
β_0	-2.146 ^{ns}	5.579 ^{ns}
β_1	1.044**	0.829**
f	0.096 ^{ns}	1.587 ^{ns}
t_{pooled}	0.072 ^{ns}	0.375 ^{ns}

^aValues followed by ** and ns are significant ($P \leq 0.05$) and not significant ($P > 0.05$), respectively; n = number of observations.

Risk prediction chart for leaf blast on RD23 sown at Uthong Field Crop Experiment Station, Suphanburi, Thailand, during 1993-1994. Infection: N = no infection; L = light (severity: 1-25%); M = moderate (severity: 27-66%); S = severe (severity: 67-100%).

have VIF values < 10 and their coefficients (β 's) have $P \leq 0.05$, which suggested uncorrelated independent variables that are important in the model.

The above equation was validated by comparing the actual and predicted severities for both fitting and validation samples (see table). The equation is useful in predicting leaf blast if the correlation coefficient (r) is > 0.85 ; the intercept (β_0) and slope parameters (β_1) have $P > 0.05$ and $P > 0.05$, respectively; and the f [modified F statistic that tests simultaneously β_0 and β_1 to be not different from zero ($P > 0.05$) and unity (≤ 0.05), respectively] and pooled t -statistic (t_{pooled}) values have $P > 0.05$ in the validation sample. We found the equation

satisfied these criteria reasonably well (see table) for both samples.

A risk prediction chart for leaf blast in Suphanburi (see figure) was developed based on the predictions of the empirical model using different values of MMAX and MWS. From the chart, moderate to high blast risk exists at MMAX of 30-38 $^{\circ}$ C and MWS of 0-2.0 ms^{-1} and a disease management intervention, such as fungicide application, may be needed. The chart also suggests that during days with 3.0 m s^{-1} windspeed, interventions would be unnecessary regardless of MMAX level, as blast would not substantially reduce rice yield. ■

Use of lesion number per leaf area to estimate lesion size for leaf blast quantitative studies

A. C. Calvero and R. S. Zeigler, IRRI

Leaf blast quantitative resistance studies to determine quantitative trait loci routinely use the parameters lesion number leaf area⁻¹ (LnA) and lesion size leaf area⁻¹ (LsA). Counting the number of sporulating lesions and measuring size using standard assessment keys make disease assessment prohibitively labor-intensive if samples are large.

A high correlation between LnA and LsA has been reported in several studies. Lesion number is easily derived by simple counts, while lesion area is probably the most biologically significant. Therefore, we propose a mathematical model to describe their relationship, estimating LsA based on LnA alone.

Data sets from two leaf blast polycyclic experiments done in the greenhouse using F₇-recombinant inbred lines (RILs) of CO 39/IAC 165 and doubled haploid (DH) lines from IR64/Azucena, including their parent cultivars, were analyzed. Replications 3 and 4 were done on a staggered basis, with each replicate separated by 2 wk. LnA and LsA data were taken 2 wk after the plants were spray-inoculated with blast spore suspension. Isolates CA42 and PO6-6 were used to infect the RILs and DH lines, respectively. A total of 1318 disease observations were generated from the inoculation work. Out of this number, 988